

Supporting Information

Metal-Organic Frameworks as efficient oral detoxifying agents

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1. Methods

Materials

All materials were commercially obtained and used without further purification.

Synthesis conditions

MIL-127 and the 3,3',5,5'-azobenzenetetracarboxylic acid ligand (H₄TazBz) were synthesized as previously reported.^[28]

MIL-127 or $[Fe_3(OH)_{0.66}Cl_{0.33}(C_{16}N_2O_8H_6)_{1.5}(H_2O)_3] \cdot nH_2O$. A mixture of 0.33 mmol of iron(III) perchlorate hydrate (Fe(ClO₄)₃·nH₂O; 118 mg), 0.33 mmol of 3,3',5,5'-azobenzenetetracarboxylic acid (H₄TazBz, 119 mg), 15 mL of N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) and 100 μL of a 5 M hydrofluoric acid solution were introduced in a 23 mL Teflon-lined vessel. The vessel was placed in a metallic Parr bomb and heated at 150 °C for 3 days. The obtained brown solid was recovered by centrifugation and washed twice with 10 mL of DMF (3 h), then, twice with 20 mL of ethanol (2 h) and, one with 20 mL of distilled water (2 h).

3,3',5,5'-azobenzenetetracarboxylic acid (H₄TazBz). 19 g of 5-nitroisophthalic acid were suspended in 250 mL of distilled water, and then, slowly, 50 g of sodium hydroxide NaOH, followed by heating at 60 °C under magnetic stirring. 100 g of glucose dissolved in 150 mL of water were slowly added to the previously obtained pink slurry. The solution turned from yellow to orange and then, brown. The heating was stopped, and air was bubbled through the solution overnight at room temperature. The mixture was cooled down with an ice-bath in order to optimize the amount of precipitate. The filtrate was then redissolved in 200 mL of distilled water and then, this solution was acidified to pH = 1 using 37% HCl. This yielded to a bright orange precipitate, recovered by filtration, and washed with ethanol.

Physicochemical characterization

¹H NMR experiments for the characterization of the synthesized ligand were recorded on an Advance Bruker Instrument (300 MHz). Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy studies (FTIR) were recorded using a Nicolet 6700 FTIR thermo scientific spectrometer in the 400–4000 cm⁻¹ region. Powder X-Ray diffraction (PXRD) patterns were collected in two different instruments: D5000 (θ - 2θ mode) Siemens diffractometer with λ (Cu $K_{\alpha 1, K_{\alpha 2}}$) = 1.54059, 1.54439 Å, and high-throughput Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer working in transmission mode and equipped with a focusing Göbel mirror producing λ (Cu K_{α}) = 1.5418 Å, and a LYNXEYE detector. Profiles were generally collected in the $3^\circ < 2\theta < 20^\circ$ range with a typical step size of 0.05° in continuous mode. N₂ isotherms were obtained at 77 K using a Belsorp Max (Bel. Japan). Prior to the analysis, approximately 40 - 60 mg of material was evacuated following a two step process: under vacuum at 200 °C for 12 h, (Belprep, Bel Japan), and then at 120 °C for 5 h under secondary vacuum directly in the Belsorp Max instrument. Field

Emission Gun Scanning Electron Microscopy (FEG-SEM) was carried out using a JEOL JSM 6335F microscope at 15 kV coupled with an Oxford Instruments X-Max 80 mm² unit. Inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) analyses were performed in a Perkin Elmer Optima 7300 DV. Samples were previously digested in 2 M HNO₃ at 60 °C overnight. Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) analyses were performed in a Thermo Electron Corporation M series AA Spectrometer.

Quantification of ASA, SA and H₄TazBz linker by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) in the in vitro studies. All analytes were determined using a reversed phase HPLC system Waters Alliance 600E, equipped with a UV-vis detector Waters W2489 and a multisampler 2707 controlled by Empower software (Waters, Milford MA, USA). A Durashell C-18 reverse-phase column (5 μm, 4.6 x 150 mm Waters) was employed. The mobile phase consisted of 50% solution (v/v) of methanol (MeOH) and phosphate buffer saline (PBS, 0.02 M, pH = 2.5). The injection volume was set at 30 μL with a flow rate of 1 mL min⁻¹ and the column temperature was fixed at 37 °C. Several methanolic ASA, SA and H₄TazBz solutions were used as standards, as previously reported.² The standard calibration curve showed a good correlation coefficient ≥ 0.99 . The chromatogram of standard solutions showed a retention time of 5.64 min (corresponding to ASA with absorption maximum at 227.9 nm), 6.76 min (identified as SA, with an absorption maximum at 231 nm) and 4.36 min (corresponding to H₄TazBz with an absorption maximum at 320 nm).

Preparation of the phosphate buffer solution (PBS, 0.04 M, pH = 2.5). 2.4 g (0.02 mol) of NaH₂PO₄ and 2.84 g (0.02 mol) of Na₂HPO₄ were dissolved in 1 L of MilliQ water. The pH was then adjusted to 2.5 with H₃PO₄ ($\geq 85\%$).

Figure S1. Calibration plots and chromatograms of (a) ASA, (b) AS, and (c) H_4TazBz standards by HPLC method.

Preparation of simulated gastrointestinal (GI) media

Gastric simulated conditions were obtained using an HCl solution at pH = 1.2 (0.137 M).

Ringer solution: Ringer medium was prepared by mixing 50 mL of solution 1 (see Table S1), and 100 mL of solution 2, NaCl (6.72 g) and NaHCO₃ (2.10 g). The final volume of the Ringer medium was adjusted to 1000 mL with MilliQ water. The compositions of solutions 1 and 2 were indicated in Table S1. The pH was adjusted to 6.00 with a 2 M HCl solution.³

Table S1. Composition of solution 1 and solution 2 used for the preparation of Ringer medium

Solution 1		
Salt	Weight (g)	Concentration (mmol·L⁻¹)
MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	4.82	1.2
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3.52	1.2
The volume was adjusted to 1000 mL with MilliQ water		
Solution 2		
K ₂ HPO ₄	4.16	2.4
KH ₂ PO ₄	0.54	0.4
The volume was adjusted to 1000 mL with MilliQ water		

Prior to all the analyses, the simulated GI media were kept at 37 °C in an incubator.

2. Stability of MIL-127 under simulated GI conditions

Stability studies were performed by suspending 30 mg of desolvated MIL-127 in 30 mL of the selected media (*i.e.* water, gastric, and intestinal). The suspensions were stirred under bidimensional continuous stirring in an incubator at 60 x 60 rpm at 37 °C for 24 h. In order to recover the solid and liquid phases, the suspensions were centrifuged at 14500 rpm during 10 minutes. PXRD, FTIR and N₂ sorption analyses were performed in order to check their stability and porosity.

Figure S2. PXRD patterns of MIL-127 after been suspended in H₂O (24 h at rt), gastric (HCl, pH = 1.2 at 37 °C for 2 h), and intestinal conditions (Ringer media pH = 6.0 at 37 °C for 24 h) compared with pristine MIL-127. The MIL-127 is stable under GI conditions since their PXRD patterns are not affected after treatment.

Figure S3. FTIR spectra of MIL-127 after suspension in H₂O (24 h), gastric (HCl, pH = 1.2 at 37 °C for 2 h), and intestinal media (Ringer media pH = 6 at 37 °C for 24 h) compared with the pristine MIL-127. Although FTIR spectra of MIL-127 are not affected after the treatments, a new band appears at *ca.* 1680 cm⁻¹ (especially under gastric conditions), probably corresponding with the presence of free ligand due to its leaching during the stability test.

Material	BET Surface (m ² g ⁻¹)
MIL-127	1260
MIL-127@H ₂ O	1130
MIL-127@Intestinal	1220
MIL-127@Gastric	960

Figure S4. N₂ sorption isotherms at 77 K for MIL-127 after treatment in H₂O (24 h), gastric (HCl, pH = 1.2 at 37 °C for 2 h), and intestinal conditions (Ringer media, pH = 6 at 37 °C for 24 h) compared with the pristine MIL-127. Close and open symbols indicate adsorption and desorption, respectively. The N₂ sorption capacity is maintained when comparing with the original MIL-127. However, the sample suspended under gastric conditions shows a decrease in N₂ uptake capacity, which can be related with the partial degradation of the material.

3. *In vitro* ASA encapsulation

It is known that after acute oral ASA overdose, a peak plasma concentration of salicylates is reached after 12 to 24 h.⁴ ASA acts as a prodrug in the human body, being hydrolyzed to salicylic acid (SA). Therefore, prior to the adsorption studies, the kinetic of ASA degradation was studied under GI conditions. For that purpose, 4 mg of ASA were suspended in 50 mL of the selected media (gastric and intestinal). The formation of SA was studied by HPLC over 24 h. Considering the important hydrolysis of ASA (*i.e.* 2 and 20% of the total ASA is transformed to SA under simulated gastric conditions for 2 h and intestinal conditions for 24 h, respectively), we determined the efficiency of the detoxification process by quantifying the encapsulation of the pristine ASA and its hydrolyzed product (SA) within the MIL-127.

Figure S5. Representation of ASA degradation to SA under (a) gastric (HCl, pH = 1.2 for 2 h), and (b) intestinal conditions (Ringer media, pH = 6.0 for 24 h) at 37 °C.

***In vitro* ASA encapsulation.** The ASA encapsulation studies were performed by firstly suspending 30 mg of MIL-127 in 30 mL of ASA gastric solution (HCl, pH = 1.2 for 2 h), and then, the recovered solid (14500 rpm, 10 min) was suspended in a fresh solution of 30 mL of ASA in an intestinal solution (Ringer media, pH = 6.0 for 24 h). Note here that the ASA adsorbed during the gastric conditions was not released after the medium exchange to intestinal conditions. ASA:MIL-127 ratio used were 1.5:1 and 3:1. The suspensions were stirred under bidimensional continuous stirring in an incubator at 60 x 60 rpm at 37 °C. At different incubation times, the suspensions were centrifuged (14500 rpm, 10 min), and supernatants were further filtered with a syringe filter (0.2 μ m) to obtain clean solutions. The obtained solids were characterized by PXRD to check their crystallinity, while the filtered supernatants were analyzed by HPLC to determine the amount of remaining salicylates and the total amount of leached ligand in the solution.

Figure S6. PXRD patterns of MIL-127 material after being suspended in gastric (HCl, pH = 1.2 at 37 °C for 2 h) and intestinal conditions (Ringer media, pH = 6.0 at 37 °C for 24 h), with different ASA:MIL-127 ratio (3:1 and 1.5:1). For comparison, pristine MIL127 is also represented. MIL-127 remains stable under GI conditions supplemented with ASA.

N₂ adsorption measurements of the ASA@MIL-127

N₂ sorption measurements of MIL-127 were performed after the ASA encapsulation experiments, using the same conditions as the *in vitro* experiments: first, the MIL-127 materials were suspended in an ASA gastric solution (HCl 2 h), and then, the recover materials were suspended in a fresh solution of ASA in an intestinal solution (Ringer media, pH=6.0 for 24 h). Two different ASA:MOF ratios (1:0.5 and 1:2) were used. A significant reduction of both the pore volume and surface area can be observed after the ASA encapsulation.

Material	BET Surface (m ² g ⁻¹)	Vp (cm ³ ·g ⁻¹)
MIL-127	1260	0.51
ASA@MIL-127 (1:0.5)	163	0.08
ASA@MIL-127 (1:2)	115	0.06

Figure S7. N₂ sorption isotherms at 77 K for MIL-127 after being suspended in gastric (HCl, pH = 1.2 at 37 °C for 2 h), and then intestinal conditions (Ringer media, pH = 6 at 37 °C for 24 h) compared with the pristine MIL-127. Close and open symbols indicate adsorption and desorption branches, respectively. The N₂ sorption capacity is significantly reduced when comparing with the original MIL-127.

Comparison with other adsorbent materials

As previously described, the ASA encapsulation studies were performed by firstly suspending 30 mg of activated charcoal or MOF in 30 mL of ASA gastric solution (HCl, pH = 1.2 for 2 h), and then, the

recovered solid (14500 rpm, 10 min) was suspended in a fresh solution of 30 mL of ASA in an intestinal solution (Ringer media, pH = 6.0 for 24 h). The suspensions were stirred under bidimensional continuous stirring in an incubator at 60 x 60 rpm at 37 °C. At different incubation times (2, 2.5, 10 and 26 h), the suspensions were centrifuged (14500 rpm, 10 min), and supernatants were further filtered with a syringe filter (0.2 µm) to obtain clean solutions. The filtered supernatants were analyzed by HPLC to determine the amount of remaining salicylates. Note here that in the case of the activated carbon and UiO-66, the ASA adsorbed during the gastric conditions was released after the medium exchange to intestinal conditions (11 and 24%, respectively). ASA used was the same (weight in activated charcoal and molar in Zr-MOFs) that the one used in the MIL-127 ratio 1.5:1 experiment, making possible the direct comparison between materials.

Table S2. Evolution of salicylates removal under simulated GI conditions (% of adsorbed salicylates) using different adsorbents.

	Gastric Media	Intestinal Media		
Time (h)	2	2.5	10	26
Norit® activated charcoal	97%	-11%	17%	34%
MIL-127	13%	7%	11%	33%
UiO-66	11%	-24%	-7%	6%
UiO-66-NH₂	13%	5%	-1%	9%

4. *In vivo* experiments

All experimental procedures were reviewed and approved by Animal Experimentation Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Pharmacy of Paris-Sud 11 University (Project number: 8314/201609191924867). Wistar female rats (4-weeks-old, 100 ± 20 g) were obtained from the central animal care facilities Janvier Labs, France. After fasting overnight, rats were randomly divided into groups of 6 animals and were housed in individual metabolic cages. Taking into account previous MOFs biodistribution studies and the quite important previously evidenced inter-individual variability, the groups were composed by 6 animals.⁵⁻⁸ All animals were maintained in an air-conditioned room (22 - 25 °C) on a 12 h light/dark cycle with water and food available.

Five different groups denoted as glucose (negative control), ASA (positive control), H₄TazBz, MIL-127, and ASA@MIL-127 were studied:

Glucose (negative control): 0.5 mL of a single dose of 10% w/v glucose solution was orally administered by gavage.

ASA (positive control): 0.5 mL of a 350 mg·Kg⁻¹ of ASA solution (in 10% w/v glucose solution) was orally administered by gavage.

ASA@MIL-127: Firstly, 0.5 mL of a 350 mg·Kg⁻¹ of ASA solution (in 10% w/v glucose solution) was orally administered by gavage. After 1 h, 1 g·kg⁻¹ of MIL-127 (the ASA:MIL-127 ratio was 1.5:1, corresponding to the dry state of the MOF) was previously dispersed in a 10% w/v glucose solution (0.5 mL) and then, orally administered by gavage.

MIL-127: Firstly, 0.5 mL of 10% w/v glucose solution was orally administered by gavage. After 1h, 1 g·kg⁻¹ of MIL-127 was previously dispersed in a 10% w/v glucose solution (0.5 mL) and then, orally administered by gavage.

H₄TazBz: Firstly, 0.5 mL of 10% w/v glucose solution was orally administered by gavage. After 1h, 0.66 g·kg⁻¹ of H₄TazBz (corresponding to the amount of linker present in 1 g·kg⁻¹ of MIL-127) was previously dispersed in a 10% w/v glucose solution (0.5 mL) and then, orally administered by gavage.

Quantification of SA and H₄TazBz linker by HPLC in serum. The quantification of SA and H₄TazBz linker was performed using the same HPLC conditions as for the *in vitro* studies. To study the pharmacokinetics (PK) profile of SA and H₄TazBz ligand, 250 µL of blood was extracted after 24 h using heparinized tubes. Blood was collected from the jugular vein opposite to the administration site. Blood was then centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 15 min, and supernatant was collected. Plasma samples were store at -20 °C. For SA and H₄TazBz determination, plasma samples were firstly diluted by adding 40 µL of phosphate buffered saline to the same volume of sample and gently mixed using vortex. Then, to extract SA and H₄TazBz, 320 µL of mobile phase were added, causing protein precipitation due to MeOH. The mixture was vigorously vortexed during 1 min.

To study the biodistribution (BD) of ASA, SA H₄TazBz and iron, all groups were sacrificed after blood collection. Stomach, duodenum, jejunum, ileum, colon, spleen, heart, kidneys, lungs and liver were extracted, and, if possible, their content was collected. Then, organs were rinsed with 0.9% NaCl and stored at -20 °C until analysis. Also, to perform the histological observation, organs were excised and fixed in 4% *p*-formaldehyde and store in EtOH solution (70%), and stained with hematoxylin and eosin routinely for histological examination. The iron distribution in different organs and feces was monitored by Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS), and Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry analyses (ICP-OES), respectively. Urine was also collected at 24 h and centrifuged (14500 rpm, 10 min). 0.1 M H₂SO₄ was added to the supernatant (10% of the urine volume). Samples were stored at -20 °C.

Quantification of ASA, SA and H₄TazBz linker by HPLC in small intestine. The quantification of ASA, SA and H₄TazBz linker was performed using the same HPLC conditions as for the *in vitro* studies. The intestinal contents were firstly diluted by adding 40 µL of PBS (0.02 M, pH = 2.5) to the same volume of intestinal sample and gently mixed using a vortex. Then, to extract ASA, SA and H₄TazBz, 320 µL of mobile phase were added (MeOH/PBS). The mixture was vigorously vortexed during 10 min, and centrifuged 5 min at 14000 rpm. 30 µL of the supernatant were analyzed by HPLC

Quantification of ASA and SA by reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) in urine samples. Urine quantification of ASA, SA and 4-aminosalicylic acid (used as internal standard, denoted IS) concentrations were determined using a RP-HPLC Agilent 1200 system equipped with a photodiode array detector (PDA), controlled by Chemstation agilent software. A C-18 Agilent LiChrospher reverse phase column (5 µm, 250 × 4.6 mm² was employed. For the quantification of all the chemical species isocratic conditions were used. The flow rate was 0.5 mL·min⁻¹, and the column temperature was fixed at 33 °C. In all cases de injection volume was 5 µL. The measurement conditions were 40:60 acetonitrile/PBS (0.05 M, pH = 3.2), retention times = 9.6 (IS), 11.2 (SA) and 12.5 min (ASA), and absorption maximum λ = 280 nm. For SA and ASA extraction, 200 µL of urine of treated animals (ASA and ASA@MIL-127 groups) were added to 200 µL of acetonitrile and 60 µL of MeOH, stirred for 10 min and centrifuged 5 min at 3000 rpm. 5 µL of the supernatant were analyzed by RP-HPLC. Urine control samples were spiked with 100 µL of a standard acetonitrile solution of IS (100 µg·mL⁻¹). Chromatograms of ASA and ASA@MIL-127 treated animals show no peaks interfering with IS, AS and ASA.

Figure S8. Chromatograms of urine extracts of spiked control urine with IS of ASA and ASA@MIL-127 groups.

Toxicity was assessed by animal behavior, body and organ weight, macroscopic observation of organs, histology studies, ASA, SA, iron and H₄TazBz ligand biodistribution, as well as different biomarkers. The normality of data distribution was tested by one-way ANOVA test. Data are shown as the mean and the standard deviation. A value of P<0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Figure S9. Concentration of (a) salicylates, and (b) H₄TazBz ligand in the contents of duodenum, jejunum and ileum expressed in mg·of salicylates *per* mL of content after 24 h. The salicylates concentration is remarkably lower after the administration of the MIL-127 when compared with the ASA control group.

Table S3. H₄TazBz concentration in small intestine

	MIL-127	ASA@MIL-127
Duodenum (mg·mL ⁻¹)	0.017±0.003	0.006±0.002
Jejunum (mg·mL ⁻¹)	0.124±0.005	0.012±0.005
Ileum (mg·mL ⁻¹)	0.124±0.002	0.010±0.004

Body and organs weight evolution

Figure S10. (a) Body and (b) organs weight of animals treated with glucose (10%, negative control), ASA (positive control), H₄TazBz, MIL-127, and ASA@MIL-127 expressed in g.

5. Histology

Stomach histology of the MIL-127 treated animals showed normal gastric mucosa, which consists of a superficial layer containing foveolae and a deep layer of gastric glands. In contrast, stomach sections of the ASA treated rats show significant histological changes expressed by an ulcer formation with cellular desquamation and necrosis of the mucosal epithelium.³⁵ By contrast, the ASA@MIL-127 and MIL-127 groups images revealed mucosal architecture free from any pathological changes induced by ASA, confirming the gastroprotective effect of MIL-127 particles, located on the surface of the mucous cells (Figure S11(b,d), black arrows).

Figure S11. Histological sections of rat gastric mucosa after 24 h of 10% glucose (negative control), MIL-127, ASA (positive control) and ASA@MIL-127 administration. Yellow arrows indicate ulcer formation and cellular desquamation (M: Mucosa, MM: Muscularis Mucosae, F: Foveolar, Gg: Gastric glands, and L: Lumen).

Likewise, jejunum histology (Fig. 3 within the main text) showed an important amount of MIL-127 material around the intestinal microvilli, which might prevent the salicylates intestinal absorption. Besides, the presence of a totally normal intestinal epithelia with intact mucosa, long and slender microvilli topography, covered by both columnar absorptive with brush border and goblet cells and intestinal crypts containing different cell types, supports the absence of any severe toxicity in MIL-127 group (Figure 3 in the main text, MIL-127(b) vs. glucose control group(a)). In contrast, the

administration of an ASA overdose produced focal erosions in the intestinal mucosa,³⁶ showing extensive intestinal damage. In particular, we can observe destruction and shortening of villi and cellular desquamation accompanied by loss of villous relief and altered enterocytes surface and brush border. Remarkably, the ASA@MIL-127 group showed reasonably well-preserved jejunum epithelia without any histological lesion. Although the normal villous relief was focally modified due to swelling and fusing of the villi (Figure 3(d), red arrows), no other alteration of the epithelium layer was observed. These results are of particular importance since they rule out the gastric and intestinal toxicity of MIL-127 that remains adhered on the microvilli, working as ASA detoxifying and gastric and intestinal mucosa protective agent.

Figure S12. Histological sections of rat livers after 24 h of 10% glucose (negative control), MIL-127, ASA (positive control) and ASA@MIL-127 administration. Yellow arrows indicate hepatic neutrophils infiltrations.

Stability studies in stomach. A 0.5 mL suspension of MIL-127 ($0.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{Kg}^{-1}$) was orally administered to Wistar female rats *via* gavage to a group of 6 animals. Then, animals were anesthetized and an incision was performed to access the duodenum in order to collect the gastric content during 1 h. The collected suspensions were stored at $-20 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Figure S13. PXR D patterns of MIL-127 material after passing through the stomach. For comparison, pristine MIL-127 is also represented. MIL-127 remains stable along the GI track. Data were collected using the D5000 Siemens diffractometer.

Figure S14. FEG-SEM images of feces of animals treated with (a) ASA and (b) ASA@MIL-127.

Iron levels. The iron level was quantified in organs (stomach, duodenum, jejunum, ileum, kidneys, heart, spleen and liver) by AAS. Plasma iron concentration was measured using the reported assay based on ferrozine.⁹

Figure S15. Fe content in different organs expressed in ug of Fe per gram of tissue. Except for duodenum and jejunum iron levels were found to be normal.

Figure S16. Iron level in plasma expressed in $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$.

Biochemical parameters. Plasma aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransaminase (ALT), amylase and lipase were spectrophotometrically determined using commercial diagnostics kits (Biomaghreb, Tunisia; Randox, United Kingdom).

Figure S17. Levels of alanine (ALT) and aspartate (AST) transaminases, amylase and lipase of treated animals compared with controls (**: $p < 0.05$, *: $p < 0.1$). This data show that although intestinal absorption of ASA is reduced in presence of MIL-127, the ASA toxicity is not fully avoided.

6. Intestinal permeability

The use of a living and intact intestinal tissue is more realistic than cell culture and provides some advantages such as: *i*) the intestinal tissue are likely to express all the transporters and the enzymes at the same “physiological” level of expression, *ii*) mucus production is maintained during the time-course of permeation experiments, and *iii*) the data obtained through living intestine can be directly correlated to *in vivo* experiments that will be conducted in the same animal model.³

The permeation Ussing chambers consist of two compartments containing Ringer media (acceptor and donor) separated by an intestinal biopsy (jejunum and ileum). Intestinal tissue from female Wistar rats was obtained after washing with 0.9% NaCl solution and mounted in the permeation chamber.¹⁰ During all the experiment, both compartments were oxygenated and circulated by bubbling with carbogen (95% O₂/5% CO₂), keeping the temperature at 37 °C. The bubbling of the solutions is an essential factor for the viability of the intestinal membranes, but also to avoid the sedimentation of the MIL-127 material. The tissue biopsies were placed into the diffusion chambers and let to stabilize during 1 h. During all the experiment, the tissue viability and integrity were controlled by monitoring the transepithelial resistant (TEER) using a potentiometer and the pH values of the donor and receptor compartments.¹¹ The biopsies were placed with the inner area of the intestine (intestinal mucosa) faced to the donor compartment and serosa to the receptor one, leaving an available diffusion area of 1 cm². ASA (0.350 mg·mL⁻¹), and/or MIL-127 (1 or 2 mg·mL⁻¹) or H₄TazBz (0.6 mg·mL⁻¹) were suspended in the donor compartment. Permeating studies were performed for 2 h at 37 °C. The intestinal permeation was monitored by collecting several aliquots (1 mL) from the receptor compartment at different times (0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 h) and replaced with the same volume of fresh medium pre-equilibrated at the experimental temperature conditions (37 °C). At the end of each experiment, the MIL-127 solid placed at the donor compartment was also analyzed by PXRD. The collected aliquots were analyzed by HPLC in order to quantify the intestinal crossing of salicylates and H₄TazBz. All the experiments were performed by triplicate for each experimental data.

The intestinal diffusion flux ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) was calculated by using the equation $F = (dQ/dt)/A$, where dQ/dt ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) represents the permeability rate, and A (cm²) is the effective surface area of the intestinal mucosa. Moreover, the permeability coefficient (P , cm·h⁻¹) was calculated by using the equation $P = F/Q$, where Q ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) is the initial concentration of the studied compound in the donor chamber.

Subsequently, the viability of the intestinal membrane was studied by measuring the conductivity of the membrane through the modulation of the ion channels. Firstly, 50 μL of forskolin were added to the donor media in order to open the ion channels, as forskolin-induced K channel activities.^{12,13} After 10 minutes, 50 μL of biotine were added in order to restart the normal membrane conditions.¹⁴

Figure S18. *Ex vivo* permeation of (a) H₄TazBz and (b) MIL-127 through the intestine (jejunum) after 2 h at 37 °C.

Figure S19. Membrane response to the addition of forskolin or biotin after 2 h of membrane permeation studies with (a) H₄TazBz and (b) MIL-127 at 37 °C.

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